

Running ML Workloads on K8s Clusters

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Agenda

- **Multi Node Training with DDP**
- **DDP Implementation for K8s Clusters**
- **Required K8s Resources**
- **Required Libraries**
- **ML Training Code**
- **Docker File**
- **Build and Deployments**

What is DDP

- Multi-node **Distributed Data Parallel (DDP)** is a technique in PyTorch that allows you to scale your deep learning training across multiple independent machines (nodes) in a cluster.
- DDP works by replicating your model on each process across all participating nodes. During training, each process gets a different subset of the training data (through a **distributed sampler**).
- After the forward pass, the gradients are computed locally on each process. DDP then handles the **synchronization** of these gradients across all processes
- DDP supports various communication backends (e.g., **NCCL**, Gloo, MPI) that can be chosen based on the network infrastructure and hardware.

[Image Credit](#)

DDP Requirements

You need to set specific **environment variables** on each node before launching the training script. These variables are used by **torch.distributed.init_process_group** to establish communication. The most important variables are:

- **MASTER_ADDR**: The IP address or hostname of the master node (the node that will coordinate the setup).
- **MASTER_PORT**: A free port on the master node that will be used for communication.
- **WORLD_SIZE**: The total number of processes participating in the training across all nodes. This is typically equal to the total number of GPUs you want to use.
- **RANK**: The unique rank of the current process. Ranks range from 0 to `WORLD_SIZE - 1`.
- **LOCAL_RANK**: The rank of the current process within the current node.

Required K8s Resources

K8s Job Resource

```
apiVersion: batch/v1
kind: Job
metadata:
  name: fine-tune-job
spec:
  parallelism: 2
  completions: 2
  completionMode: Indexed
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        app: fine-tune
    spec:
      restartPolicy: Never
      serviceAccountName: fine-tune-sa
      containers:
        - name: fine-tune-container
          imagePullPolicy: Always
          image: rezabah/distilbert-ft:v1
          # Command is set in the Dockerfile ENTRYPOINT; arguments below will be appended
          args:
            - "--experiment_name=experiment-${JOB_ID}"
            - "--batch_size=${BATCH_SIZE}"
            - "--epochs=${EPOCHS}"
            - "--learning_rate=${LEARNING_RATE}"
            - "--shared_fs_path=/shared"
            - "--train_dataset_range=${TRAIN_DATASET_RANGE}"
            - "--eval_dataset_range=${EVAL_DATASET_RANGE}"
          env:
            # Distributed training environment variables:
            - name: POD_NAME
              valueFrom:
                fieldRef:
                  fieldPath: metadata.name
            - name: NAMESPACE
              valueFrom:
                fieldRef:
                  fieldPath: metadata.namespace
            - name: NODE_RANK
              valueFrom:
                fieldRef:
                  fieldPath: metadata.annotations['batch.kubernetes.io/job-completion-index']
```

Required K8s Resources

```
- name: WORLD_SIZE
  value: "2" # Total number of processes (2 nodes * 1 GPU per node)
- name: NNODES
  value: "2" # Total number of nodes
- name: NPROC_PER_NODE
  value: "1" # Number of GPUs per node
- name: MASTER_ADDR
  value: "master-service" # Headless service of the master node
- name: MASTER_PORT
  value: "29501" # Port for DDP communication
- name: JOB_ID
  valueFrom:
    fieldRef:
      fieldPath: metadata.name # Unique value for the job
- name: BATCH_SIZE
  value: "16"
- name: EPOCHS
  value: "3"
- name: LEARNING_RATE
  value: "2e-5"
- name: TOKENIZERS_PARALLELISM
  value: "false"
- name: TRAIN_DATASET_RANGE
  value: "4000" # Default value for training dataset range
- name: EVAL_DATASET_RANGE
  value: "400" # Default value for evaluation dataset range
resources:
  requests:
    memory: "10Gi" # Minimum memory guaranteed for the pod
    cpu: "4" # Minimum CPU guaranteed for the pod
  limits:
    memory: "150Gi" # Maximum memory the pod can use
    cpu: "12" # Maximum CPU the pod can use
    nvidia.com/gpu: "1"
volumeMounts:
- name: shared-fs
  mountPath: /shared
volumes:
- name: shared-fs
  persistentVolumeClaim:
    claimName: shared-fs-pvc
```

Required K8s Resources

Headless Service for Master Service:

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: master-service
spec:
  clusterIP: None
  selector:
    app: fine-tune
    role: master
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 29501 # Port for DDP communication to master node/pod
    targetPort: 29501
```

Required K8s Resources

Persistent Volume:

```
# pvs for training
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: shared-fs-pvc
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteOnce
  resources:
    requests:
      storage: 1Ti
  storageClassName: csi-mounted-fs-path-sc
```

Required K8s Resources

Service Account, Role and RoleBinding:

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: ServiceAccount
metadata:
  name: fine-tune-sa
```

```
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
kind: Role
metadata:
  name: pod-labeler
rules:
- apiGroups: [ "" ]
  resources: [ "pods" ]
  verbs: [ "get", "update", "patch" ]
```

```
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
kind: RoleBinding
metadata:
  name: pod-labeler-binding
subjects:
- kind: ServiceAccount
  name: fine-tune-sa
  namespace: finetune
roleRef:
  kind: Role
  name: pod-labeler
  apiGroup: rbac.authorization.k8s.io
```

Required Libraries

transformers

datasets

torch

huggingface_hub

huggingface_hub[hf_xet]

numpy

tensorboard

scikit-learn

tqdm

ML Training Code

```
import argparse
import os
import torch
import torch.distributed as dist
import torch.multiprocessing as mp
from torch.nn.parallel import DistributedDataParallel as DDP
from torch.utils.data import DataLoader, DistributedSampler
from datasets import load_dataset
from transformers import (
    AutoTokenizer,
    AutoModelForSequenceClassification,
    get_scheduler,
    DataCollatorWithPadding
)
from tqdm.auto import tqdm

def setup(rank, world_size):
    """Initialize the process group for distributed training."""
    local_rank = int(os.environ["LOCAL_RANK"]) # Local rank (GPU index on the current node)

    # Initialize the process group
    dist.init_process_group("nccl", rank=rank, world_size=world_size)

    # Set the device to the local rank
    torch.cuda.set_device(local_rank)

    # Debug information
    print(f"[Rank {rank}] Process group initialized.")
    print(f"[Rank {rank}] Backend: {dist.get_backend()}")
    print(f"[Rank {rank}] World Size: {dist.get_world_size()}")
    print(f"[Rank {rank}] Master Address: {os.environ.get('MASTER_ADDR', 'Not Set')}")
    print(f"[Rank {rank}] Master Port: {os.environ.get('MASTER_PORT', 'Not Set')}")
    print(f"[Rank {rank}] Current Device: {torch.cuda.current_device()}")
```

ML Training Code

```
def cleanup():
    """Destroy the process group after training."""
    dist.destroy_process_group()

def train(rank, world_size, args):
    """Main training function for each process."""
    # Setup distributed training
    setup(rank, world_size)

    # Debug: Print rank-specific information
    print(f"[Rank {rank}] Starting training with world size {world_size}.")
    local_rank = int(os.environ["LOCAL_RANK"])

    # Load dataset
    dataset = load_dataset("glue", "sst2")
    train_dataset = dataset["train"].shuffle(seed=42).select(range(args.train_dataset_range))
    eval_dataset = dataset["validation"].select(range(args.eval_dataset_range))

    # Load tokenizer
    model_name = "distilbert-base-uncased"
    tokenizer = AutoTokenizer.from_pretrained(model_name)

    # load model
    model = AutoModelForSequenceClassification.from_pretrained(
        model_name,
        num_labels=2,
        ignore_mismatched_sizes=True
    ).to(local_rank)

    # Preprocess datasets
    def preprocess_function(examples):
        return tokenizer(examples["sentence"], truncation=True, padding="max_length", max_length=128)
```

ML Training Code

```
train_dataset = train_dataset.map(preprocess_function, batched=True)
eval_dataset = eval_dataset.map(preprocess_function, batched=True)
dist.barrier() # Ensure all ranks finish mapping

train_dataset.set_format("torch", columns=["input_ids", "attention_mask", "label"])
eval_dataset.set_format("torch", columns=["input_ids", "attention_mask", "label"])

# Distributed sampler
train_sampler = DistributedSampler(train_dataset, num_replicas=world_size, rank=rank, shuffle=True)
eval_sampler = DistributedSampler(eval_dataset, num_replicas=world_size, rank=rank, shuffle=False)

# Data loaders
data_collator = DataCollatorWithPadding(tokenizer=tokenizer)
train_dataloader = DataLoader(train_dataset, sampler=train_sampler, batch_size=args.batch_size, collate_fn=data_collator)
eval_dataloader = DataLoader(eval_dataset, sampler=eval_sampler, batch_size=args.batch_size, collate_fn=data_collator)

# Wrap model with DDP
model = DDP(model, device_ids=[local_rank])

# Optimizer and scheduler
optimizer = torch.optim.AdamW(model.parameters(), lr=args.learning_rate)
num_training_steps = args.epochs * len(train_dataloader)
lr_scheduler = get_scheduler("linear", optimizer=optimizer, num_warmup_steps=0, num_training_steps=num_training_steps)

# Training loop
for epoch in range(args.epochs):
    model.train()
    train_sampler.set_epoch(epoch) # Shuffle data for each epoch
    progress_bar = tqdm(train_dataloader, desc=f"Epoch {epoch + 1} [Global Rank {rank}]")
    #progress_bar = tqdm(train_dataloader, desc=f"Epoch {epoch + 1} [Global Rank {rank}]", disable=rank != 0)
    for batch in progress_bar:
        batch = {k: v.to(local_rank) for k, v in batch.items()}
        outputs = model(**batch)
        loss = outputs.loss
        optimizer.zero_grad()
        loss.backward()
        optimizer.step()
        lr_scheduler.step()
        progress_bar.set_postfix({"loss": loss.item()})
```

ML Training Code

```
# Evaluation loop
model.eval()
eval_loss = 0
correct = 0
total = 0
with torch.no_grad():
    for batch in eval_dataloader:
        batch = {k: v.to(local_rank) for k, v in batch.items()}
        outputs = model(**batch)
        predictions = torch.argmax(outputs.logits, dim=-1)
        labels = batch["labels"]
        loss = torch.nn.functional.cross_entropy(outputs.logits, labels, reduction="sum")
        eval_loss += loss.item()
        correct += (predictions == labels).sum().item()
        total += labels.size(0)

eval_loss /= total
accuracy = correct / total
# if rank == 0:
    print(f"Epoch {epoch + 1}: Eval Loss = {eval_loss:.4f}, Accuracy = {accuracy:.4f}")

# Save the model (only on rank 0)
if rank == 0:
    output_dir = os.path.join(args.shared_fs_path, args.experiment_name)
    os.makedirs(output_dir, exist_ok=True)
    model.module.save_pretrained(output_dir)
    tokenizer.save_pretrained(output_dir)
    print("Training complete!")

cleanup()

def main():
    # Read environment variables set by torchrun
    world_size = int(os.environ["WORLD_SIZE"]) # Total number of processes
    rank = int(os.environ["RANK"]) # Global rank of the current process
    local_rank = int(os.environ["LOCAL_RANK"]) # Rank of the process on the current node

    print(f"Starting training with world size {world_size}, rank {rank}, and local rank {local_rank}.")

    parser = argparse.ArgumentParser()
    parser.add_argument("--batch_size", type=int, default=16, help="Batch size per GPU")
    parser.add_argument("--epochs", type=int, default=3, help="Number of training epochs")
    parser.add_argument("--learning_rate", type=float, default=2e-5, help="Learning rate")
    parser.add_argument("--experiment_name", type=str, default="default-experiment", help="Name for this experiment")
    parser.add_argument("--shared_fs_path", type=str, default="/shared", help="Path to shared filesystem")
    parser.add_argument("--train_dataset_range", type=int, default=1000, help="Number of training samples to use")
    parser.add_argument("--eval_dataset_range", type=int, default=200, help="Number of evaluation samples to use")
    args = parser.parse_args()

    train(rank, world_size, args)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

ML Training Code - Notes

Initialization of Distributed Training (setup function):

This step initializes the process group using `torch.distributed.init_process_group`. This sets up the communication backend (in this case, "nccl" which is optimized for GPUs) and establishes connections between the different processes (nodes/GPUs) involved in the distributed training. It also sets the current process's GPU device based on its local rank.

Loading Dataset:

The code uses the `datasets` library to load the "glue" dataset, specifically the "sst2" task (a sentiment analysis dataset). It then shuffles the training data and selects a subset of both the training and validation datasets based on the `train_dataset_range` and `eval_dataset_range` arguments.

Loading Tokenizer:

An `AutoTokenizer` is loaded based on the "distilbert-base-uncased" pretrained model. The tokenizer is responsible for converting the raw text data into numerical inputs that the model can understand.

Loading Model:

An `AutoModelForSequenceClassification` is loaded, also based on the "distilbert-base-uncased" pretrained model. This model is a DistilBERT model with a classification head on top, suitable for sequence classification tasks like sentiment analysis. The model is then moved to the specific GPU assigned to the current process (`local_rank`).

ML Training Code - Notes

Preprocessing Datasets:

A `preprocess_function` is defined to tokenize the "sentence" column of the datasets. This function truncates and pads the sequences to a maximum length of 128. The map function is then used to apply this preprocessing function to both the training and evaluation datasets in batches.

Synchronization After Preprocessing (`dist.barrier()`):

This step ensures that all distributed processes have finished the potentially time-consuming data preprocessing step before proceeding further. This is crucial to prevent issues where some processes might be waiting for data that hasn't been fully prepared by others.

Setting Dataset Format:

The format of the training and evaluation datasets is set to "torch", and the relevant columns ("input_ids", "attention_mask", "label") are specified. This prepares the datasets to be used with PyTorch DataLoader.

Creation of `train_sampler` and `eval_sampler`:

`DistributedSampler` is created for both the training and evaluation datasets. These samplers are responsible for partitioning the data across the different processes in the distributed training setup. Each process will only receive a subset of the data based on its rank and the total number of processes (`world_size`). The `train_sampler` shuffles the data within its partition for each epoch, while `eval_sampler` does not.

ML Training Code - Notes

Creation of train_dataloader and eval_dataloader:

DataLoader instances are created for the training and evaluation datasets. These data loaders provide an iterable over the datasets, yielding batches of data. The sampler argument is set to the respective DistributedSampler, ensuring that each process only iterates over its assigned portion of the data. DataCollatorWithPadding is used to pad the sequences within each batch to a consistent length.

Wrapping the model with DDP:

The loaded model is wrapped with DistributedDataParallel (DDP). This is the core of PyTorch's distributed training capability. DDP handles the communication of gradients between the different processes during the backward pass, ensuring that the model weights are updated consistently across all processes. The device_ids argument specifies which GPU the model should reside on for the current process.

Setting up the optimizer and scheduler:

An AdamW optimizer is initialized with the model's parameters and a specified learning rate. The AdamW optimizer is a common choice for training Transformer models.

A learning rate scheduler (get_scheduler) is set up. In this case, a "linear" scheduler is used, which will linearly decrease the learning rate over the course of training. The num_warmup_steps is set to 0, and num_training_steps is calculated based on the number of epochs and the size of the training data loader.

Entering the training loop:

The code then enters a loop that iterates for the specified number of epochs.

ML Training Code - Notes

Training Epoch:

Inside each epoch, the model is set to training mode (`model.train()`).

The `train_sampler`'s epoch is set to the current epoch number to ensure different shuffling of data in each epoch across the distributed processes.

The code iterates through the `train_dataloader`, processing batches of training data.

For each batch:

The batch is moved to the current GPU.

The model's forward pass is performed to get the output (including the loss).

The gradients are reset using `optimizer.zero_grad()`.

The loss is backpropagated using `loss.backward()`.

The optimizer updates the model's parameters using `optimizer.step()`.

The learning rate scheduler updates the learning rate using `lr_scheduler.step()`.

A progress bar (only visible on rank 0) displays the training progress and the current loss.

ML Training Code - Notes

Evaluation loop:

After each training epoch, the model is set to evaluation mode (`model.eval()`).

Variables are initialized to track evaluation loss, correct predictions, and total number of samples.

The code iterates through the `eval_dataloader` without calculating gradients (with `torch.no_grad()`).

For each batch:

The batch is moved to the current GPU.

The model's forward pass is performed to get the output logits.

Predictions are obtained by taking the argmax of the logits.

The evaluation loss is calculated using cross-entropy.

The number of correct predictions and the total number of samples are accumulated.

Evaluation Metrics Reporting:

After evaluating the entire evaluation dataset, the average evaluation loss and accuracy are calculated.

If the current process is rank 0, these evaluation metrics are printed.

ML Training Code - Notes

Saving the Model:

After all epochs are completed, if the current process is rank 0, the trained model's state and the tokenizer's configuration are saved to a specified output directory on the shared filesystem. Saving is typically done only by the master process to avoid redundant saves.

Cleanup (cleanup function):

Finally, the cleanup function is called to destroy the distributed process group, releasing the resources used for distributed training.

Docker File

```
# Dockerfile
FROM nvidia/cuda:12.4.1-cudnn-runtime-ubuntu20.04

# Install dependencies
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y python3 python3-pip iputils-ping curl ca-certificates && \
    rm -rf /var/lib/apt/lists/*

# Ensure 'python' points to 'python3'
RUN ln -s /usr/bin/python3 /usr/bin/python

# Install kubectl
RUN curl -LO "https://dl.k8s.io/release/$(curl -L -s https://dl.k8s.io/release/stable.txt)/bin/linux/amd64/kubectl" && \
    chmod +x kubectl && \
    mv kubectl /usr/local/bin/

# Modify /etc/gai.conf to prioritize IPv4
RUN echo "precedence ::ffff:0:0/96 100" >> /etc/gai.conf

# Set environment variable for PATH
ENV PATH="/root/.local/bin:$PATH"

# Create working directory
WORKDIR /app

# Copy requirements.txt (create one with necessary packages)
COPY requirements.txt .
RUN pip install --upgrade pip
RUN pip install -r requirements.txt

# Copy the rest of application
COPY fine-tune.py .
RUN chmod +x fine-tune.py
# Copy the entrypoint script
COPY entrypoint.sh .
RUN chmod +x entrypoint.sh

# Set the entrypoint to use the script
ENTRYPOINT ["/app/entrypoint.sh"]
```

Entrypoint Shell Script

```
#!/bin/bash
# Entry point script for distributed training with PyTorch DDP using torchrun

# Debugging information
echo "NODE_RANK=${NODE_RANK}"
echo "WORLD_SIZE=${WORLD_SIZE}"
echo "NNODES=${NNODES}"
echo "NPROC_PER_NODE=${NPROC_PER_NODE}"
echo "MASTER_ADDR=${MASTER_ADDR}"
echo "MASTER_PORT=${MASTER_PORT}"

if [ "${NODE_RANK}" -eq "0" ]; then
    echo "Labeling the master pod: ${POD_NAME} with role=master"
    kubectl label pod "${POD_NAME}" -n "${NAMESPACE}" role=master --overwrite
fi

exec torchrun \
    --nproc_per_node=${NPROC_PER_NODE} \
    --nnodes=${NNODES} \
    --node_rank=${NODE_RANK} \
    --master_addr=${MASTER_ADDR} \
    --master_port=${MASTER_PORT} \
    fine-tune.py "$@"
```

Build and Deployments

```
docker build -t rezabah/distilbert-ft:v1 .  
docker push rezabah/distilbert-ft:v1  
kubectl apply -f pvc.yaml -n finetune  
kubectl apply -f role.yaml -n fine-tune  
kubectl apply -f rolebinding.yaml -n finetune  
kubectl apply -f master-service.yaml -n finetune  
kubectl apply -f fine-tune-job.yaml -n finetune
```

Thank you

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